

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES
№3 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9556-2022-3>

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ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

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COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF PRODUCTIVITY IMPROVEMENTS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6717922>

ANNOTATION

If we want to achieve labor efficiency and its sustainability, we need to thoroughly study all the factors that positively and negatively affect it and create the necessary set of measures. In other words, labor processes need to be managed optimally using complex methods. It is known that labor and its efficiency are the largest economic and social synthetic indicator. At present, the growth of labor productivity is expressed in more effective development and use of human resources, especially their intellectual properties. This is confirmed by the active development of the digital economy and the growing demand for specialists with high intellectual qualities, including digital competencies. This trend is particularly determined by changes in the labor and employment model and the expansion of digital labor opportunities. In this regard, in order to increase labor productivity in the conditions of digitalization of all spheres of activity, it is necessary to form, develop and implement modern technologies for the use of intellectual resources. The article discusses the technologies of using intellectual property of labor resources in accordance with the modern realities of economic development in the context of the trend of digitalization.

Keywords: product quality; digital economy; digital opportunities; soft skills; teamwork; digital labor; labor productivity; volume of work.

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MEHNAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING KOMPLEKS TAHLILI

ANNOTASIYA

Agar biz mehnat samaradorligini va unga barqaror erishib turishni istasak, unga ijobiy va salbiy ta'sir qiluvchi barcha omillarni har tomonlama chuqur o'rganib, kerakli chora-tadbirlar majmuasini yaratishimiz kerak. Boshqachasiga aytganda, mehnat jarayonlarini kompleks usullarni qo'llagan holda optimal darajada boshqarish lozimdir. Ma'lumki, mehnat va uning samaradorligi eng katta iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy sintetik ko'rsatkichdir. Hozirgi vaqtda mehnat unumdorligini oshirish inson

resurslarini, ayniqsa, ularning intellektual xususiyatlarini yanada samarali rivojlantirish va ulardan foydalanishda namoyon bo'ladi. Buni raqamli iqtisodiyotning faol rivojlanishi va yuqori intellektual xususiyatlarga ega, jumladan, raqamli kompetentsiyalarga ega mutaxassislariga talab ortib borayotgani ham tasdiqlaydi. Ushbu tendentsiya, xususan, mehnat va bandlik modelining o'zgarishi va raqamli mehnat imkoniyatlarining kengayishi natijasida shakllanadi. Shu munosabat bilan faoliyatning barcha sohalarini raqamlashtirish sharoitida mehnat unumdorligini oshirish maqsadida intellektual resurslardan foydalanishning zamonaviy texnologiyalarini shakllantirish, ishlab chiqish va joriy etish zarur. Maqolada raqamlashtirish tendentsiyasi sharoitida iqtisodiy rivojlanishning bugungi realliklariga mos keladigan mehnat resurslarining intellektual xususiyatlaridan foydalanish texnologiyalari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: mahsulot sifati; raqamli iqtisodiyot; raqamli vakolatlar; jamoaviy ish; raqamli mehnat; mehnat unumdorligi; ish hajmi.

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КОМПЛЕКСНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ РОСТА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТРУДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Если мы хотим добиться эффективности труда и его устойчивости, нам необходимо досконально изучить все факторы, положительно и отрицательно влияющие на него, и создать необходимый комплекс мероприятий. Иными словами, трудовыми процессами необходимо оптимально управлять комплексными методами. Известно, что труд и его эффективность являются крупнейшим экономическим и социальным синтетическим показателем. В настоящее время рост производительности труда выражается в более эффективном развитии и использовании человеческих ресурсов, особенно их интеллектуальных свойств. Это подтверждается активным развитием цифровой экономики и растущим спросом на специалистов с высокими интеллектуальными качествами, в том числе цифровыми компетенциями. Эта тенденция особенно определяется изменениями в модели труда и занятости и расширением возможностей цифрового труда. В связи с этим для повышения производительности труда в условиях цифровизации всех сфер деятельности необходимо формировать, разрабатывать и внедрять современные технологии использования интеллектуальных ресурсов. В статье рассматриваются технологии использования интеллектуальной собственности трудовых ресурсов в соответствии с современными реалиями развития экономики в условиях тенденции цифровизации.

Ключевые слова: качество продукта; цифровая экономика; цифровые возможности; мягкие навыки; работа в команде; цифровой труд; производительность труда; объем работы.

With regard to such a resource as labor, productivity in modern economic research is considered as a broad an economic category that reflects ideas not only about the effectiveness of the labor factor, but also covers most aspects of the organization's activities. Traditionally, the economic content of labor productivity is considered as fruitfulness, productivity of people's production activities, i.e. the ability of specific labor to create a certain amount of output (value added) per unit of working time (Table 1).

Table 1.

Definition	Source
The productivity of the production activity of people, measured by the amount of products produced per unit of working time.	Dictionary of the Russian language: In 4 volumes / USSR Academy of Sciences, Institute of Russian. lang.; Under the editorship of A.P. Evgenieva. – 3rd ed., stereotype. - M., 1985-1988. T. 3 P-R. 1987. - 752 p.
An indicator of the efficiency of the use of labor resources, the labor factor. It is measured by the quantity of products in physical or monetary terms, produced by one employee for a certain time (hour, day, month, year).	Dictionary, ed. Borisova A.B. “Great Economic Dictionary. - M., 2003. - 895 p.
An indicator of the efficiency of the use of labor resources, the labor factor. It is measured by the quantity of products in physical or monetary terms produced by one employee for a certain, fixed time (hour, day, month, year).	Raizberg B.A., Lozovsky L.Sh., Starodubtsev E.B. /Modern Economic Dictionary. – 4th ed., revised. and additional - M., 2004. - 480 p.
Efficiency of specific work. It is measured by the number of products, operations created or completed per unit of time, or by the amount of time spent per unit of labor product.	Big Economic Dictionary / Ed. A.N.Azrilian. - 7th ed., add. - M., 2007 - 1472 p.
A generalizing indicator of labor productivity, characterized by the volume of output per unit of labor, reflecting the degree of progressiveness of the labor force, equipment, technology, and management. At the same time, it should take into account the efficiency of the use of capital.	Morozova N.A. Labor productivity: theoretical foundations and factors of growth in the modern economy: Dis. ... cand. economy Sciences / N.A. Morozov. – 2007 – 156 p.
Aggregate labor productivity is an indicator of the economic efficiency of the functioning of the resources expended in economic activity, characterizing the contribution of the industry (region, firm) to the increment in the value of the final product in the economy and reflecting the degree of progressiveness of management, development of human capital, technology, technology and science.	Kuchina E.V. Ensuring the competitiveness of industrial enterprises on the basis of increasing the productivity of aggregate labor: theory and methodology: Dis. ... doc. economy Sciences / E.V. Kuchina. - 2009. - 321 p.
An indicator of labor efficiency that characterizes the competitiveness of a country, region, industry, enterprise, product and is the main source of economic growth.	Mitrofanova M.Yu. Labor productivity in the modern economic system: Dis. ... cand. economy Sciences /M.Yu.Mitrofanova. - 2010. - 218 p.
The share of output or services rendered per unit of labor input.	Labor Economics: textbook / A.I. Rofe. - M., 2010. - 400 p.

It is known that the development of society, the welfare of the people, the prosperity of the country, the level of human potential and capital, especially the future life, as well as all dreams and

beauty, the average life expectancy also depends on labor productivity and its constant growth. Hence, labor and its efficiency are the largest economic and social synthetic indicators. In addition, the level of labor productivity determines the method of production, the means, and even the socio-political system itself.

The origin of the problem of «labor productivity» was formed in the XVIII century under the influence of ideas embodied in the concept of economic liberalism. Adam Smith believed that the development of production had a direct impact on the welfare of the country. One of the main factors in his vision of the economic system is the division of labor, because it is the division of labor that leads to an increase in labor productivity. Adam Smith believed that the division of labor increases productivity in three ways:

- increase the agility of each individual employee;
- saving time when moving from one type of activity to another;
- to stimulate the invention and production of machines that facilitate human labor [1].

M.Keynes also thought about labor productivity, he recommended increasing the level of employment in the state and shortening the working day to stimulate production growth. The free time can be spent by workers on intellectual, physical self-development [2, 379-380].

Thus, it can be concluded that labor productivity research in the twentieth century is mainly focused on the study of the efficiency of human capital. In today's market conditions, each enterprise must organize and operate a system of planning and management of production development in order to maximize labor productivity [3].

Labor productivity is understood mainly in economic, social, psychophysiological, organizational, technological and environmental aspects. In order to achieve efficiency and stabilize it, it is necessary to take into account the factors that depend on it and various influences, and to study and analyze them using economic, social, psychophysiological methods.

The growth of labor productivity is of great importance for individual enterprises and society as a whole, it is necessary to study all the factors that affect the level of labor productivity and to open reserves to increase it [2, 95-96].

According to the principle of taxonomy, the factors of labor productivity under consideration can be divided into 3 types [4, 1119-1123].

1. Factors related to resource management:
 - personnel department;
 - capital (technical means and investments);
 - energy;
 - materials;
 - information
2. Factors related to the form of interaction:
 - technological;
 - economic;
 - hulq-atvor;
 - political; systemic; process
3. Factors related to the size of the unit of the analyzed enterprise:
 - individual; grouped; the whole enterprise.

If we want to achieve labor efficiency and its sustainability, we need to thoroughly study all the factors that positively and negatively affect it and create the necessary set of measures. In other words, labor processes need to be managed optimally using complex methods.

The main aspects of it are the creation of sanitary and hygienic conditions for people, ensuring safety at work, ensuring the content of labor, adherence to the division of labor, creating opportunities for the development of mental and physical strength during labor, the ability to form social norms important in labor organization. formation, creation of a series of various economic, social incentives that motivate employees, and most importantly - to achieve a level of employee satisfaction with their work.

Labor productivity is mainly measured by two indicators, namely quantity and quality. Achieving a minimum level of labor costs is of great importance in increasing labor productivity and efficiency. Labor productivity is mainly determined by the volume of work per unit of time, the number of employees and the quality of labor.

Labor productivity indicators can also include:

- labor productivity and its dynamics;
- changes in product production;
- quality of labor;
- professional skills and qualifications of employees;
- mental and physical labor of the person spent on the work performed;
- save working time;
- efficient and rational use of working time.

Labor productivity and its efficiency are also one of the mainstays of the gross product - national income. The volume of labor productivity depends on the potential, creative potential, social attitude of employees in production and non-production, the proper functioning of the balance of justice in the organization, social justice, the morale of managers and employees, the strength of the legal framework, the level of technology and energy. the key is more dependent on employees' attitudes and beliefs about the future.

Ensuring continuous labor productivity and its sustainable efficiency is the main task of every enterprise, sector, government and state. What to do for this? First, the fields of science, science and forecasting in the field of labor must be brought to a constant and high level. Expanding the scope of scientific and practical work in this area, training highly qualified personnel and the division of labor in various fields, labor organization, labor incentives, qualitative and quantitative study of labor resources, various economic, social, legal experiments in the field of labor, labor remuneration. to raise it to the level of world standards, to limit unnecessary expenses in labor enterprises and to carry out economic and social policy in the field of labor at the modern level, to eliminate unemployment and achieve optimal employment in all regions, etc. It is also important to constantly develop integration between them, while paying attention to both internal and external factors in the constant increase of labor productivity.

Another key way to increase labor productivity is to create and implement a socio-economic program of labor organizations. Such a program takes into account all the elements of labor and organizational management.

The organization takes into account technology, technology, social management, economic mechanisms, information systems and management technologies and their integration links, and creates a constant control - sociological monitoring. The company will create a common statistical base and use it to improve management and forecast the future of productivity in the near and long term.

As the great scientist and philosopher Confucius said, our future depends on the prediction we make. Another key way to continuously increase labor productivity is to create and implement mathematical and statistical models that take into account the economic, sociological, psychological, physiological, environmental and external influences that affect it.

In general, increasing productivity means either life or death. Therefore, the development of science, education, upbringing and ensuring the connection between them is a very large, necessary, integrated and scientific-practical policy. This will be achieved through the creation and implementation of the following socio-economic model. When this is achieved, the level of human health is restored and life expectancy is constantly increasing.

In our opinion, first of all, it is necessary to develop a clear and unambiguous scientific basis for the program of socio-economic development in the near, medium and long term, as well as forecasts for integrated development in all regions, industries, with interconnectedness. The program takes into account all the indicators and indicators that determine social and economic development, and through them all the statistical analysis and other quantitative aspects are developed.

Also, first of all, social and economic databases must be fully implemented. To do this, it is formed in 2 different directions, ie through sociological research and economic-statistical data for at least 10-15 years. Socio-economic programs are formed, first of all, vertically, that is, from bottom to top and from top to bottom, and in parallel. The program consists of several stages and steps. In the first stage, it will be created in small and medium governmental and non-governmental organizations. The second phase will be created in the remaining large organizations and corporations. In the third stage, all management is carried out in all network systems.

In the fourth stage, the program will be created in all rural areas, neighborhoods, districts, cities and regions. In the fifth stage, the program of socio-economic development of the republic as a whole will be created in terms of all the programs are integrated with each other, both in terms of statistics and in terms of the rules of all other integrations.

At the same time, all resources in Uzbekistan are digitized and their volume is calculated. I have created an algorithmic system that takes into account the most advanced computer technologies of our time and all the mathematical methods, which are performed in all 5 stages in a unique and consistent way.

In the first phase of the program, 5 or 10 year statistical data on all social and economic indicators of state and non-state enterprises and institutions will be analyzed on a scientific basis. After that, a plan for the coming years will be prepared for each enterprise and institution, and medium and long-term forecasts will be made.

As a result of practical and scientific work, the unique and appropriate development of each enterprise and institution is determined. At the heart of this is the resource base for the development of each enterprise, and at the same time the dynamic growth of its key indicators is calculated. The main indicators here are the formation of highly qualified personnel, the emergence of a trend of ever-increasing labor productivity, reducing the cost of services and products, and minimizing the consumption of labor and other resources. And at the same time, as a result of scientific calculations and analysis, the future, near and distant future of each organization and institution will be determined. Thus, in stages 2, 3, 4 and 5, a report of scientific analysis and forecasts is conducted, which also determines the current and future socio-economic image of each object.

In general, it is necessary to ensure the mutual integration of programs created in 5 types of objects. In this case, a balancing process is ensured in the development of socio-economic development. This, in turn, leads to sustainable development and a steady increase in the well-being of society.

The development and implementation of socio-economic development programs at all facilities will not only ensure a steady increase in labor productivity, but also a gradual increase in life expectancy as a result of increasing human potential.

Much more can be done to ensure that labor productivity continues to grow. In particular, taking comprehensive measures to increase human potential requires, first of all, the rapid development of the education system and the implementation of modern reforms. A clear example of this is the policy of education development in the new Uzbekistan since 2017. As stated in a number of resolutions and decrees of the President, the construction of human potential at the level of modern requirements begins in kindergarten. Due to this, a completely new system of education has been established in our country. That is, today the Ministry of Preschool Education is functioning.

At the expense of the secondary school education, the most modern technology is being created for its development. After all, the quality of secondary education paves the way for a steady increase in the quality of higher education. Significant changes are also taking place in the system of secondary special and higher education. The state pays more attention to the development of the teaching staff, which is a key link in the education system.

Today's educators are respected as teachers and have earned the highest reputation. Today, the level of moral and material incentives for professors and teachers is growing rapidly, as a result of which the quality of education is increasing tremendously. Of course, it is well known that in the past and present, the human potential of Uzbekistan is not very high, but it is growing rapidly as a result of reforms in the near future. Such attention and expenditures by the state will ensure that in the near

future the human potential of our country will grow to a high level. It is clear that the development of human potential will ensure the growth of labor productivity in all areas.

In the classical sense, an indicator of labor efficiency is its productivity, which is measured by the amount of product produced per unit of working time. However, our goal is not in material production, but in determining the effectiveness of labor in education and science. The usual definition of labor productivity in relation to this field is, of course, incorrect. That is, according to this definition, to increase labor productivity in education and science should be understood as an increase in the labor of a professor and (or) researcher without the ability to evaluate the final result. For example, in the calculation of the labor productivity of production workers, defects in production are excluded from these calculations. It is unknown how to assess such shortcomings in higher education. It is clear that such a problem plan needs to be adapted to the learning process. This means that the increase in labor efficiency in the field of education exceeds the established norms (number of lectures per day, graduate work prepared by students per 1 university professor-teacher per year) leads to a decrease in the quality of student education. It is logical to assume that labor productivity in such complex areas focused on intangible results as education and science cannot be determined as in production, and it is expedient to consider other indicators related to them [5, 145].

The great importance of labor productivity growth for individual enterprises and society as a whole requires the study of all the factors that affect the level of labor productivity and the disclosure of resources to increase it. Factors are forces, causes, external circumstances that affect a process or event. Depending on the degree and nature of the impact on the level of labor productivity, the factors can be divided into three groups: material-technical, organizational, economic and socio-psychological [6].

Another factor influencing labor productivity is the elimination of unemployment in every space and industry. Unemployment can lead to various negative situations. That is, an increase in various crimes, an increase in diseases, the emergence of mental states among people, and one of the greatest harms can become a major factor in hunger and poverty. The main ways to deal with such a major tragedy is to accelerate the rapid growth of small and medium-sized businesses based on innovative approaches in every place and place. Relieving every country from hunger and poverty as soon as possible also depends on this issue [7].

Today, not only the unemployed, but also every able-bodied person, young and old, regardless of their field, is engaged in entrepreneurship. Such a situation can now be observed in several states. For example, in China, 70% of the gross domestic product is made up of small and medium-sized businesses. In developed countries - Norway, Germany, Korea, Israel, Turkey and others, the share of small and medium-sized businesses in GDP is high.

The development of small and medium-sized businesses today needs to be transformed not only into public policy, but also into a nationwide affair. There are several other factors that can save nations from poverty, including:

First, raising the morale of the people living in each country to a higher level is a matter of urgency.

Secondly, it is necessary to raise the level of culture of the society in each region, to form a real human image in the people, to put an end to all oppression and war in the world.

Third, it is time to get rid of the scourge of terrorism in the world and in some countries and to put an end to human trafficking.

Fourth, it is necessary to develop medicine in the fight against all diseases that occur in the world and lead to the destruction of humanity, and to create a single medical scientific system among all countries.

Fifth, the elimination of groups of states that lead to all the negative situations in the world and at the same time strengthen the dominance of a single UN is a requirement of the times.

Sixth, it is the dream of our century to completely eliminate alcohol, various drugs and psychotropic substances, cigarettes and other harmful habits that cause great material and spiritual harm to people [8].

It is necessary to create unique mechanisms and technologies that will ensure a constant increase in labor productivity. Creating this requires the use of complex methods, technologies and equipment. These include the methods, mechanisms and processes of sociological research, as well as the use of complex mathematical and statistical methods. As a result, a single scientific-practical universal management system of labor productivity has emerged, through which it will be possible to ensure that labor productivity is science-based and constantly growing. Such a model and system is created based on the specific conditions, resources, techniques and technologies of each country's territory.

For example, the model of increasing labor productivity in the Republic of Uzbekistan is unique and relevant. While such a system has a common view model for each enterprise, each network, and each region, the information that corresponds to it may vary. If such a system and model of labor productivity is created for all countries around the world, and put into practice, it is possible to have a material wealth of enormous size. And this wealth can save humanity from death and starvation until the end of our century.

It should be noted that there are many negative events in the world of humanity that can happen in March and hinder the socio-economic development of society. Examples include strong storms, earthquakes, floods, terrible tsunamis in the seas and oceans, rising global temperatures from year to year, abnormal changes in the weather in some places, and the occasional serious medical epidemic. The fact that the 19 virus has become a pandemic will have very serious economic consequences and social losses for all states and societies. In particular, the pandemic, which has been going on since March 2020, has not left any country unharmed, and has brought severe economic and social disasters to many countries. Uzbekistan is no exception. Due to the decline in the gross domestic product of our country, the living standards of the people have fallen, and the army of the unemployed has increased. If this situation continues for a long time and other horrific events occur frequently, it has undoubtedly become clear that 30-40% of the people on earth lack food for the peoples. This is on the one hand.

On the other hand, the size of the globe – the area under crops – has not changed, and demographic growth continues. This situation is having a huge negative impact on people's lives.

On the other hand, the amount of water needed for irrigation is declining. As a result of the deterioration of the ecological situation, the number of pests has also increased, causing significant damage to crops. Such an objective reality poses to humanity a very large and urgent problem.

To identify solutions to labor productivity problems, we highlight key objectives and the labor productivity factor. The main goals that lead to increased production efficiency are: - reducing costs and increasing profitability; - Reducing the cost of materials - increasing the flexibility of production; - Improving the quality of goods and services; - Improving production processes [9, 200-202].

How to feed humanity today and in the future, keep it healthy and provide for future generations poses a huge question to humanity. Is there a way out of a very difficult situation? and if so? In this regard, no later than today, the whole of humanity must unite, using reason and understanding, science and enlightenment, honesty and justice, to form a single fist, to form a high level of human potential and through it to have a solution to the problem. Experts, intellectuals and scientists from all over the world must work together to create a social, economic and mathematical model for solving the above problem. We believe that only in this way can humanity save itself from any difficult situation and create a comfortable living environment for itself [10].

The solution to the problem can be summarized and the following measures and suggestions can be made.

First, it will be necessary to develop social mechanisms, technologies and models that are important for human life.

Second, to identify economic, organizational, environmental, technical and other factors affecting labor productivity through analysis of variance and correlation. Expressing the extent of their impact on labor productivity in mathematical models. Probability theory and the mathematical statistical model of labor productivity can be created by using all the mathematical and statistical methods to determine the factors that affect labor productivity in all respects and quantify the degree

of impact of each of them and ultimately create a mathematical model. First of all, it is necessary to use everything from the simplest to the most complex methods. It is also possible to create mathematical models that are worthy of obtaining an optimal calculation of labor productivity, making extensive use of both theoretical and practical methods of higher mathematics. It should be noted that the widespread use of innovative methods in the creation of this model is also recommended.

One of the most important tasks in optimizing labor productivity is to create a database of social and economic statistics. Formal, statistical information can be widely used in the creation of the economic base, and the formation of social information is of some complexity. To this end, complex, sociological research is carried out, taking into account the social conditions on the ground, and their sociological analysis is carried out. Of course, here the laws of statistics, for example, statistical information collected on a random basis, must be complied with in accordance with the law of representativeness of statistics. Calculations made using a mathematical model obtained as a result of a complex approach should be specific to a particular object and a particular period. Over time, it is considered necessary to update the database of social and statistical information and revise the reports, taking into account objective factors.

Third, to be able to form a spiritual image that is inherent in people in all states and societies.

Fourth, to ensure a high level of relations between all states, nations and religions.

Fifth, it is necessary to create and implement a complex, innovative, mathematical model of specific and appropriate labor productivity in each group, enterprise, industry, region.

It is well known that ensuring the constant growth of human labor productivity is the law of life. In order to fulfill this law, all nations and peoples must unite all their forces and work together in unity.

It is well known that the proverb is true, and no force can defeat the united. We, the authors, call not only the people of Uzbekistan, but also the countries and peoples of the world to unity and cooperation. After all, we have the power to solve any difficult and complex problem together through intellectual power.

A strong fight against poverty and destitution has begun in Uzbekistan, and there is no doubt that the social and economic policies pursued are correct and scientifically sound.

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ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

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